

DEFECT LOCATION IN STRUCTURES MADE FROM ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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A method is described for non-destructively assessing the integrity of structures using measurements of the structural natural frequencies. It is shown how measurements made at a single point in the structure can be used to detect, locate and roughly to quantify damage. One set of frequencies is measured before the structure is put into service, subsequent measurements being used to test whether the structure is still sound. Alternatively, measurements at an intermediate stage may be used as a baseline and the progress of damage monitored from this stage.

The presence of damage can be detected simply from changes in the natural frequencies of the structure. Location and the assessment of the severity of the damage, however, require a dynamic analysis of the structure to be carried out. This may be performed using any convenient mathematical technique and only one such analysis is required for each type of structure to be tested.

Results are presented from a straight bar, an automobile camshaft, fibre composite plates and honeycomb panels obtained from the aerospace industry. It is shown to be possible to detect and locate a variety of forms of damage including fatigue cracks and impact damage in fibre composite structures which is barely visible yet causes severe reductions in the strength of the laminate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Adams et al. [1] found that damage in specimens fabricated from fibre reinforced plastics could be detected by a reduction in stiffness and an increase in damping, whether this damage were localised, as in a crack, or distributed through the bulk of the specimen as many microcracks. This change in stiffness resulted in a decrease in the natural frequencies of the specimen. Also, since the stress distribution through a vibrating structure is non-uniform and is different for each natural frequency (mode), any localised damage would affect each mode differently, depending on the particular location of the damage. The measurement of the natural frequencies of a structure at two or more stages of its life therefore offers the possibility of detecting the presence of damage and of locating its position. The size of the frequency changes may also be related to the severity of the damage. If one set of frequencies were measured before the structure were put into service, subsequent frequency measurements could be used to test whether the structure were still sound. Changes in damping could be used in exactly the same manner for locating defects.

Measurement of the dynamic characteristics, that is the natural frequencies and damping, of a structure is potentially a very attractive form of non-destructive test since these properties can be measured at a single point on the structure and are independent of the position chosen. A test based on these measurements would therefore not require access to the whole of the structure and would not involve time-consuming scanning of the whole surface. The time taken to perform the test can be very small, particularly if a transient test technique [2, 3] is employed. An efficient method for obtaining accurate natural frequencies from such a test has been described by Cawley and Adams [4].

The authors [5] successfully tested the frequency measurement principle on structures which could be treated as one-dimensional and later extended the method to two-dimensional and, potentially, to three-dimensional structures [6, 7]. The presence of damage could be detected simply by noting changes in the natural frequencies of the structure. Location and assessment of the severity of the damage, however, required that a dynamic analysis of the structure be carried out. This analysis had to be sufficiently accurate to give a reasonable indication of the mode shapes.

The dynamic analysis of the one-dimensional structures considered in Ref. 5 was carried out using receptance techniques [8]. There is no multi-dimensional equivalent of receptance analysis, so another method had to be used in the later work. The finite element technique was chosen as it is well-documented [9], accurate, and can be used to analyse any structure. The technique described in Refs. 6 and 7 is therefore potentially applicable to all structures. However, in situations where a closed form analysis can be employed, the use of finite element analysis tends to be relatively inefficient in terms of computational effort and, since the basic principle of the method of damage location is not dependent on the type of analysis used, it would sometimes be advantageous to use another mathematical technique. The results from the damage location routine developed in Refs. 6 and 7 are more easily interpreted than those from the scheme used in Ref. 5, so it would be desirable to develop this routine for use with other methods of analysis.

This paper unifies the approaches of Refs. 5, 6 and 7, showing the requirements for the dynamic analysis, which can be carried out using any convenient method, and how the results from this are used, together with the experimentally measured frequency changes, as input to a separate program for the location and estimation of the severity of the damage.

The technique can be used with any type of structural vibration, that is, torsional, axial, flexural or any combinations of these. When testing one-dimensional structures, it was convenient to use axial or torsional modes, but this is not practicable with shell type structures, so the tests on two-dimensional components were carried out using flexural vibration.

2. THEORY

2.1 The method of damage location

The change in the natural frequency of mode i of a structure due to localised damage is a function of the position vector of the damage, \underline{r} , and the reduction in stiffness caused by the damage, δK . Thus

$$\delta\omega_i = f(\delta K, \underline{r}) \quad (1)$$

Expanding this function about the undamaged state ($\delta K = 0$) and ignoring second order terms yields

$$\delta\omega_i = f(0, \underline{r}) + \delta K \frac{\partial f}{\partial(\delta K)}(0, \underline{r}) \quad (2)$$

But $f(0, \underline{r}) = 0$, for all \underline{r} since there is no frequency change without damage. Hence,

$$\delta\omega_i = \delta K g_i(\underline{r}) . \quad (3)$$

Similarly,

$$\delta\omega_j = \delta K g_j(\underline{r}) \quad (4)$$

Thus, provided that the change in stiffness is independent of frequency,

$$\frac{\delta\omega_i}{\delta\omega_j} = \frac{g_i(\underline{r})}{g_j(\underline{r})} = h(\underline{r}) \quad (5)$$

The ratio of the frequency changes in two modes is therefore only a function of the damage location. Positions where the theoretically determined ratio $\delta\omega_i/\delta\omega_j$ equals the experimentally measured value are therefore possible damage sites.

2.2 Computation of the frequency changes due to damage

In order to locate the position of the damage, it is necessary to determine the relative changes in the natural frequencies of the structure due to damage at a given site. Damage may be modelled as a local decrease in the stiffness of the structure. This may conveniently be introduced into the analysis by, for example, reducing the elastic modulus of the structure over a small region. Since, from Eq.(5), the relative magnitudes of the frequency changes in different modes are independent of the severity of the damage assumed in the calculation, the size of the reduction in stiffness used is immaterial.

With closed form techniques, such as receptance analysis, the computational effort involved in carrying out a dynamic analysis is fairly modest, so it is feasible to compute the frequency changes due to damage by analysing the undamaged structure and then repeating the analysis with damage at different sites. With finite element analysis, however, the amount of computer time involved using this approach would be prohibitive. A very attractive alternative to this procedure is to use a sensitivity (perturbation) analysis [10] to compute the frequency changes due to small changes in the structural stiffness. This is done using the mode shapes of the undamaged structure determined from an initial full dynamic analysis. The computational requirements are therefore reduced to one full dynamic analysis plus a small amount of time for the sensitivity analysis.

2.3 Presentation of the results of the location scheme

With a one-dimensional structure, measurement of the frequency changes in one pair of modes will yield two or more possible damage sites, that is, points where the ratio of the experimentally determined frequency changes equals the theoretical ratio. The use of further mode pairs will reduce the number of possible sites though, with symmetrical structures, two sites will always be predicted. In two- or three-dimensional configurations, each pair of modes will yield a locus of

possible damage sites. The loci for several pairs of modes may be superimposed, the actual site being given by the intersection of the loci. Again, if the structure is symmetrical, two or more sites will be predicted, the number depending on the degree of geometric symmetry and the elastic symmetry of the structural material. Because the frequency changes tend to be small and the model of damage is unsophisticated, it is desirable to use several mode pairs so that some averaging of the results is obtained. This scheme has been implemented, but it was found to be difficult to automate the plotting of the loci which meant that they had to be plotted manually. This procedure was very tedious, particularly when a large number of mode pairs was used.

An alternative was to output the relative frequency changes in the different modes due to damage at a series of grid points and to compute an error function at each point which was a measure of the error in assuming the damage to be at that point. The point at which the error was a minimum gave approximately the position of the damage.

We define the error in assuming the damage to be at position \underline{r} , given frequency changes $\delta\omega_i$ and $\delta\omega_j$ in modes i and j respectively, as

$$e_{rij} = \left. \begin{aligned} & \frac{s_{ri}/s_{rj}}{\delta\omega_i/\delta\omega_j} - 1, \quad \frac{s_{ri}}{s_{rj}} > \frac{\delta\omega_i}{\delta\omega_j} \\ & \frac{\delta\omega_i/\delta\omega_j}{s_{ri}/s_{rj}} - 1, \quad \frac{s_{ri}}{s_{rj}} < \frac{\delta\omega_i}{\delta\omega_j} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

The total error, $e_{\underline{r}}$, in assuming the damage to be at position \underline{r} is the sum of the errors in all the mode pairs. Thus,

$$e_{\underline{r}} = \sum_{i,j} e_{rij} \quad (7)$$

To aid interpretation, this error is normalised with respect to the minimum value of the total error. The final value output to the damage location chart being

$$E_{\underline{r}} = \frac{100 e_{\min}}{e_{\underline{r}}} \quad (8)$$

The most probable damage site(s) is therefore that (or those) where $E_{\underline{r}} = 100$.

This method may be used with any type of structure and has been employed for all the tests reported here.

2.4 Summary of the requirements of the method

The method for damage location and estimation of its severity requires that the frequency changes in the modes of interest (usually up to ten of the lower structural modes) due to a local reduction in the stiffness of the structure at each of a series of grid points be computed.

3. TEST PROCEDURE

The basic requirement of the method is reproducibly to determine several natural frequencies of the structure under consideration. It does not matter whether the boundary conditions are exactly the same as those assumed in the dynamic analysis provided that they are reproducible and the mode shapes are not greatly altered from those predicted by the theoretical model. Since this criterion

is easily met, a variety of methods of exciting and detecting the vibrational response may be used. The best method to use in industrial applications would probably be the transient test, in which the response of the structure to an impulse is recorded and the natural frequencies computed by Fourier transform techniques. Unfortunately, the necessary equipment was not available when these tests were carried out, so the results presented here were obtained using steady-state measurements which are slower and more difficult to perform.

The modes used in the non-destructive test were those which could easily be excited. With one-dimensional structures, the first three axial modes were usually used while, with two-dimensional structures, up to ten of the lower flexural modes were considered. Some symmetrical structures have two or more modes at the same frequency, the mode excited in practice being a combination of the two depending on the position and nature of the excitation. In these cases, it is impossible accurately to determine the mode shape. Modes of this type were therefore not used in the location scheme.

4. RESULTS

Over forty tests have been carried out on one- and two-dimensional structures with a variety of forms of damage including holes, saw cuts, fatigue cracks, impact damage and local heating. It has been shown to be possible to use the proposed technique to detect and locate all these forms of damage. Only a representative sample of the results is presented here. Further results are given in Refs. 5-7, 14 and 15. The dotted lines on the location charts for the two-dimensional structures show the finite element mesh used in the dynamic analysis.

A set of tests was performed on a trapezoidal, cross-ply carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) plate which was cut from a square plate of side 250 mm and thickness 2.8 mm fabricated from HT-S carbon fibre in DX 210 epoxy resin. This plate was damaged with saw cuts, the first being 2.5 cm long at the position shown in Fig. 1. The location chart shown in Fig. 1 relates to this case. Since the plate was asymmetrical, the damage site is uniquely defined on the chart. The second cut was of a similar size but was approximately at right angles to the first and at the same site. The location chart for damage comprising the two cuts together is shown in Fig. 2.

If the technique described here were to be used as an in-service test with measurements being made periodically, it would be important to be able to detect and locate changes in the condition of the structure, not only with respect to the virgin condition but also with respect to a stage where some damage was present. In order to test the method under these conditions, a location chart was produced using the frequency changes between the first and second sets of damage. This is shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the damage is again successfully located.

Fig. 4 shows the location chart for a 0, 60, 30, 90, 30, 60, 0° CFRP plate of thickness 3 mm and longest side of length 240 mm. This plate was damaged by placing it on a thick-walled 35 mm tube, resting a 25 mm diameter steel ball on the plate at the centre line of the tube and striking the ball with a hammer. The resulting damage was almost invisible apart from a small dent and some slight surface cracking. It has been the experience of the aerospace industry [16] that this type of damage can cause a 50 per cent reduction in the strength of the laminate and is difficult to detect other than by ultrasonic measurements which are not always practicable for the routine testing of large structures. It can be seen from Fig. 4 that the damage was successfully located by the vibration measurements.

Two structures were tested which are more representative of the ways in which high quality fibre reinforced materials are used in industry. The first of these was a 610 x 520 x 10 mm honeycomb panel with CFRP facings which is used for floor panelling in aircraft. The panel was made asymmetrical by removing one corner and was damaged by heating one face with a gas flame. This produced a large blister on this face but the damage was invisible from the remote side. Fig. 5 shows that the damage was successfully located.

Fig. 1 Location chart for CFRP plate with single saw cut

The second structure obtained from the aerospace industry was a honeycomb panel which had CFRP facings with layers oriented at 0, 90, +45, -45° and which had CFRP inserts along each edge with a total of 45, 10 mm holes drilled in them. The overall dimensions of the panel were 490 x 210 x 4 mm. The structure was modelled crudely for the dynamic analysis by ignoring the effect of the edge inserts and treating the component as a uniform panel. Damage was applied by crushing with a 25 mm steel ball in a hydraulic press, the first time with the opposite side supported so that only one face was damaged and the second time at the same site without this support, which resulted in damage to both faces. The location chart for the second set of damage is shown in Fig. 6. In this case, symmetry dictated that two possible sites be indicated. In spite of the crude model used, the damage was still accurately located. This indicates that it is unnecessary to expend large amounts of effort and computer time in order to produce an accurate dynamic analysis of the structure. The basic requirement that the mode shapes be obtained reasonably accurately is readily met.

Fig. 2 Location chart for CFRP plate with two saw cuts; frequency changes computed with respect to virgin frequencies

The method described in Section 2.5, for estimating the severity of the damage in terms of the size of a hole which would produce the same frequency changes as those measured, predicted that the first set of damage was equivalent to a hole removing 0.13 per cent of the area of the panel while, after the second application of damage, the predicted area increased to 0.20 per cent of the area. These values corresponded to measured areas of 0.10 and 0.30 per cent respectively. These results are typical of those obtained from this analysis and show that the method can be used to obtain a potentially useful indication of the severity of the damage.

1	2	3	3	5	4	2	3	5	8	13	7
2	2	3	4	7	9	3	4	7	16	15	7
3	6	6	7	13	11	4	4	5	13	13	7
3	9	11	10	18	10	4	3	6	11	8	5
4	15	22	9	8	4	3	4	7	7	8	3
5	28	36	9	9	1	2	4	7	6	6	3
8	74	82	11	2	1	5	8	12	8	4	2
19	100	43	12	3	3	7	12	14	9	3	2
29	70	19	8	7	11	14	19	11	6	3	1
42	34	12	11	15	13	15	21	11	8	3	1
19	5	11	12	13	10	6	12	9	7	4	2
12	12	11	15	15	8	2	10	8	10	7	3

damaged area indicated by ultrasonic C-scan

Fig. 4 Location chart for 0, 60, 30, 90, 90, 30, 60, 0° CFRP plate with impact damage

12	8	3	3	3	6	8	4	2	3	6	5
16	11	6	4	4	10	9	4	3	4	7	10
22	14	6	7	14	19	17	6	3	4	12	19
34	9	8	14	25	38	31	11	4	4	16	25
66	25	7	11	33	50	20	10	3	4	15	13
34	30	11	20	29	14	10	10	4	6	10	11
43	45	18	23	12	20	20	13	7	5	9	7
100	79	28	31	39	51	43	28	11	4	3	7
53	64	20	35	32	30	31	31	12	2	3	5
33	38	14	16	15	15	18	18	9	7	2	4
23	27	21	18	8	8	6	7	12	4	1	
20	20	15	9	5	9	10		9	7		

area of blister

Fig. 5 Location chart for honeycomb panel damaged by local heating

damaged area

3	2	3	2	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	2
2	3	4	5	3	1	2	4	6	3	3	2
3	5	6	7	3	1	3	4	17	4	5	3
2	6	7	100	9	1	2	17	7	4	6	2
2	6	5	8	6	1	1	10	4	6	5	2
2	6	4	3	3	1	1	6	3	5	5	2
2	5	5	3	6	1	1	3	3	4	6	2
2	5	6	4	10	1	1	6	8	5	6	2
2	6	4	7	17	2	1	9	100	7	6	2
3	5	4	17	4	3	1	3	7	6	5	3
2	3	3	6	4	2	1	3	5	4	3	2
2	3	3	2	2	2	1	1	2	3	2	3

Fig. 6 Location chart for honeycomb panel with CFRP edge inserts damaged by crushing

5. CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown to be possible to detect and locate damage in a wide variety of one- and two-dimensional structures by using measurements of the structural natural frequencies. The method can also be used to estimate the severity of the defect. The technique can be used to detect any form of damage which reduces the stiffness of the structure in a direction which is significantly stressed by the type of vibration used and this is the case with most of the forms of damage likely to be encountered in service.

The proposed test requires access to only one point of the structure and is potentially very quick to perform. One set of frequencies is measured before the component is put into service and subsequent measurements are used to determine whether the structure is still sound. Alternatively, a set of frequencies measured at an intermediate stage can be used as the initial frequencies and the growth of damage from this state monitored.

The presence of damage is detected simply from changes in the natural frequencies without the need for any analysis. The location and estimation of the severity of the damage, however, requires a dynamic analysis of the structure to be carried out. Only one such analysis is required for each type of structure to be investigated and tests have shown that the model used need not be sophisticated since the only requirement of the technique is that the mode shapes of the lower structural natural frequencies be adequately approximated, this criterion being readily met by simple representations of complex structures.

Tests have shown that damage equivalent to a crack through one per cent of the cross-sectional area of a one-dimensional structure at a single section can be detected. With two-dimensional structures, damage equivalent to the removal of about 0.1 per cent of the area of the structure can be located.

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